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The Relationship perceived organizational justice, Psychological Contract Breach and organizational citizenship behavior of physical education teachers

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was studying the relationship between perceived organizational justice, Psychological Contract Breach and organizational citizenship behavior of physical education teacher Tehran province sites. Research method was descriptive-correlation.

The statistical population was all of physical education in Tehran province cities (include 1582 peoples). The sample of statistical according to Krejcie & Morgan sampling table was 314 peoples. The data analysis was accomplished descriptive and inflectional statistic. The instrument was organizational justice (Neihoff & Moorman, 1993), organizational citizenship behaviors (Lee & Allen, 2002) and Psychological contracts breach (Rousseau, 1995), questionnaires. The results were showed the relationship between organizational justice and Psychological contracts breach with organizational citizenship behaviors. Also, organizational justice prospects Psychological contracts breach. The results of regression analysis showed Psychological contracts breach, organizational justice inconsistent 49.86 percent of variation of organizational citizenship behaviors.

Keywords: organizational justice, psychological contract breach, organizational citizenship behavior, physical education teacher

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